

Enhancing Pigeon pea production in India through precision agriculture

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Abstract

Background: Pigeon pea is an important commercial pulse crop for the farmers of Karnataka a south Indian state. Though the crop has been cultivated for many years in the region, the yield somehow is not up to desired levels due to uncertainties of rainfall extremities, conventional variety, seed rate, spacing and plant population and poses challenge towards sustainability in production.

To counteract this, the technical intervention by adopting principles of precision agriculture like use of right input in right time in right quantity in right manner like direct seeding of pigeon pea in main field to replace the conventional method of drill sown seeds so as to maintain adequate plant population for compensating yield loss is being explored as a suitable strategy to help enhance yield/productivity, improve quality with greater resource use efficiency and avoiding soil, air and food pollution.

Method: In this context, an experiment in farmers fields (25) under farmers' participatory was taken up during 2016 Kharif season with the objectives of studying the feasibility and its suitability in the area for further refining the technology of direct seeding of pigeon pea. Three varieties viz., GRG-811, BSMR-736 and ICPH-2740 with 500 grams of seeds (2900 seeds) bio- treated were sown under 6' X 3' spacing with protective irrigation during the crop growth.

Results: The study revealed that, there was 100 percent germination and crop stand with optimum number of branches with pods in all the three genotypes tested with yield levels varied with genotypes ranging from 700 to 1200 Kgs of grains and an additional seed yield to the tune of 30.00 percent was realized under dibbling and was largely attributed to 10 % higher pods/ plant.

Discussion: Due to adequate space, light and air, the crop performed well.

Conclusion: Thus the study confirmed the feasibility of adopting principles of precision agriculture in pigeon pea farming.

Key Words: Precision Agriculture, Pigeon pea, India, Dibbling, Karnataka, Right input.

Background

Pigeonpea [*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Mills.] is an important grain legume in the semi-arid tropics of Asia and Africa due to its high protein (20-22%) content. India is the largest producer and consumer because pigeonpea plays an important role in food security, balanced diet and alleviation of poverty (Rao et al. 2002). Globally pigeonpea occupies 4.6 m ha area in 21 countries with annual production of 3.4 million tons with a productivity of 893 kg/ha (Mula and Saxena 2010).

Pulses being important sources of natural vegetable protein and dietary constitution of daily life of millions world over particularly in developing countries, the year 2016 was declared by the UN as 'International Year of Pulses' to invigorate the efforts of pulse production globally. In India, pigeonpea covers 3.5 m ha area with 2.4 million tons production having a low productivity of 685 kg/ha. The productivity of pigeonpea has remained low and stagnant over the last few decades thus this prompted scientists to breed hybrid pigeonpea. Pigeonpea, commonly known as redgram, arhar or tur, is an important commercial crop for dry land farmers of Karnataka a South Indian State. "The crop owes its popularity to the fact that being a leguminous plant, it is capable of fixing atmospheric nitrogen and thereby restores nitrogen content in the soil. Its deep rooting system helps in extracting nutrients and moisture from deeper soil layers thus making it suitable for rain fed condition. Karnataka is one of the important pulses growing state in India and pulses are grown in an area of about 24.32 lakh ha with the production of 15.24 lakh tonnes and the productivity was 626 kgs/ha during 2014-15. (Anon., 2015). The important pulses grown in Karnataka are pigeonpea, chickpea, horsegram, greengram and blackgram. More than 60 per cent of the area under total pulses in Karnataka is covered by pigeonpea and chickpea crops. The major pulse growing districts in Karnataka are

Kalaburagi, Vijayapura, Bagalakot, Belagavi, Bidar, Raichur, Dharwad, Koppal and Mysuru. Though the crop has been cultivated for many years in the region, the yield somehow is not up to desired levels due to use of low yielding varieties, poor level of management practices, particularly plant protection measures, high plant population, not adopting proper agronomic practices, damage due to drought or heavy rains in rain fed areas, spread of pests and diseases, imbalanced use of fertilizers, lack of awareness on integrated nutrient management and maintenance of soil fertility. However, often local cultivars and production practices predominate and, therefore, pulse production still is not lucrative to the grower as it thought to be. Therefore, to counteract this, with a specific objective of technical intervention by adopting principles of precision agriculture like use of right input in right time in right quantity in right manner like direct seeding (dibbling) of pigeon pea in main field to replace the conventional method of drill sown seeds so as to maintain adequate plant population for compensating yield loss is being explored as a suitable strategy to help enhance yield/productivity, improve quality with greater resource use efficiency and avoiding soil, air and food pollution. The experiment was conducted under Agricultural Extension Education Centre, Koppal district of University of Agricultural Sciences, Raichur, falling in the northern dry zone of Karnataka a farmers-participatory investigation on precise technological intervention was undertaken in pigeon pea crop mainly through introduction of improved cultivars and establishing geometry during growing season of 2016 with the following objectives:

- To adopt and demonstrate precision sowing/spacing techniques in pigeon pea
- To adopt appropriate precision farming machinery/equipment to increase the input use efficiency
- To impart training to the farmers and the officials of the line departments through demonstration on precision farming techniques in pigeon pea

Method

Under the AEEC, a training programme on production technologies of pigeonpea was conducted to the pulse farmers of Koppal district, Karnataka. Cultivars, planting technologies such as transplanting, wider spacing, seed dibbling, controlled and protective irrigation etc. were given emphasis. Then interested farmers were further provided with half-a kg of microbially enriched (*Rhizobium*, PCB and *Pseudomonas*) seeds of different cultivars. Over 30 farmers of different villages with limited irrigation facility were finally chosen and were asked to dibble the seeds in 1.8/1.5 m X 0.9 m spacing and were periodically advised about aftercare. Finally, 25 farmers who have followed the suggestions satisfactorily were considered for the study. Data on number of pods per plant, yield and insect pest incidence was collected and subjected for 't' test as per procedure. There was large deviation in the data as the soils, cultural practices and management/involvement level of farm manager varied.

Study area

The experiment was conducted in 25 Villages of Koppal District. Koppal district situated in the north-eastern dry zone (Zone-II, Region-3) of Karnataka state at 15° 09' and 16°34'N latitudes and 75° 46' and 77° 35' E longitudes and is at an elevation of 401.5 m above the mean sea level. The region receives 86.5 per cent of the annual rainfall during south-west monsoon i.e., from June to September.

Area of experimentation: 1 acre each

Variety/hybrid used during experimentation: GRG-811, BSMR-736 and ICPH-2740 (hybrid)

Method of sowing:

Experiment: Dibbling

Farmers' practice: Drill sowing

Quantity of seeds used for direct seeing (dibbling):

Experiment: 500 gram per variety (approx.2900 seeds) for one acre

Farmers' practice: 5.0 Kg per acre

Spacing used for sowing:

Experiment: 180 cm X 90 cm

Farmers' practice: 45 cm X 10 cm

Irrigation schedule: Protective irrigation during critical stages of crop growth

The soils are sandy and clay loam with PH ranging from 7.0 to 8.0. The organic carbon content varied from 0.45 to 0.55 per cent. The sowing was undertaken soon after the receipt of normal rainfall during the month of June and July in 2016. Nipping of apical or terminal shoot was done by hand clipping at 50,50 and 70 and 50,70 and 90 DAS was compared with control plot (no nipping).

6° and 36°N, and 68° and 98°E.

11°30' and 18°30' N 74° and 78°30' E 15° 09' and 16°34'N and 75° 46' and 77° 35' E

Results

The data on yield components, seed yield, are presented in Table 1 and 2. The differences in the seed yield differed significantly among the three pigeonpea genotypes. The study revealed that, there was 100 percent germination and crop stand with optimum number of branches with pods in all the three genotypes tested with yield levels varied with genotypes ranging from 700 to 1200 Kgs of grains and an additional seed yield to the tune of 30.00 percent was realized under dibbling and was largely attributed to 10 % higher pods/ plant. All the improved genotypes introduced to farmers in the region fared significantly superior to local cultivar with and yield advantage ranging from 71 to 131 per cent (Table 1). One farmer informed as high as 2500 kg ha⁻¹ yield (data not presented). Of all, BSMR 736 recorded numerically higher yield and responded better to local situations. Farmers also expressed their satisfaction about recently released cultivar GRG 811 by the University which was earlier by over a fortnight from cv. BSMR 736.

Similar to improved cultivars, wider planting geometry and seed dibbling is another simple technological intervention that revealed significant yield benefits (Table 2). The improvement in yield with wider spacing (1.8 m X 0.9 m) was to the extent of 58.9 per cent over local practice of closure spacing of 0.45 m X 0.10 m. The yield benefits with wider spacing could be related to production of more number of filled pods per plant (81.6 %) under wider spacing compared to narrower spacing and significant reduction in *Heliothis armigera* and *Maruca vitrata* incidence.

Discussion

Increasing the plant density per unit land area increases the interplant competition, because higher competition between plants contribution of yield components per plant with 90 cm x 20 cm were lower when compared to 120 cm x 90 cm spacings but the loss in yield attributes per plant was compensated through higher plant population per hectare. Due to adequate space, light and air, the

crop performed well. Wider spacing allowed better light interception of light, and air movement within the crop canopy, while reducing interplant competition which helped in improving individual plant performance and harvest index. This was further facilitated by reduced incidence critical insects which could be attributed to two reasons. In local practice of closure spacing, because of interlocking of branches and canopies air movement was restricted and dense canopy provided better foraging in addition to escape from insecticidal spray drifts. Secondly, the dense canopy also reduced effective spray coverage. There are opportunities for adoption of precision agricultural techniques around the globe. The form of precision practices may be different from one place to another place, depending upon the creative mindset of farmers, practitioners, scientists and consultants local to the area of interest. There are several examples of precision nutrient management practices from several countries where farmers and practitioners have overcome the challenges and converted them into opportunities by harnessing the global information and developing local precision techniques suitable for their region, operation and resources (Raj Khosla, 2010, MB Patil et al. 2012).

Conclusion

Thus, two simple and precise interventions involving improved cultivar (cvs. BSMR, ICPH and GRG 811) and planting geometry (1.8 m X 0.9 m) in a farmer-participatory approach proved the scope and effectiveness of precision technological intervention in overall betterment productivity and production of pigeon pea in the northern dry zone of Karnataka. Thus the study confirmed the feasibility of adopting principles of precision agriculture in pigeon pea farming.

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Table 1. Performance of three cultivars under precision farming v/s local variety n geometry

Sl.No.	Seed rate (Kg/ha)	No.of plants/ha	No.of pods/plant			Yield (Kg/ha)						<i>M.vitrata</i> (larvae/plant)		
			V1	V2	V3	V1	V2	V3	V1	V2	V3	V1	V2	V3
1	1.2	6098	360.6	350.0	345.5	2223.5	1976.0	1729.9	3.5	4.0	5.0	7.1	7.4	7.6
2	1.2	6098	401.5	380.7	370.6	2324.2	2065.5	1830.5	3.0	5.0	5.5	8.0	9.0	9.0
3	1.2	6098	345.4	330.3	315.5	2085.6	1945.7	1695.5	4.5	3.3	3.0	10.1	12.0	13.6
4	1.2	6098	415.6	400.0	385.2	2470.3	2320.3	2011.1	3.3	4.0	5.5	9.5	10.3	11.5
5	1.2	6098	430.1	410.1	398.7	2700.0	2512.2	2215.7	3.1	4.1	4.5	9.9	10.0	10.5
6	1.2	6098	345.3	300.6	275.5	2010.2	1978.5	1812.3	4.5	5.0	5.6	10.0	11.0	11.5
7	1.2	6098	450.8	400.5	350.2	2845.7	2621.1	2385.9	3.0	4.1	4.7	8.5	9.1	10.0
8	1.2	6098	416.0	390.5	355.7	2555.4	2375.9	2045.1	4.8	5.0	6.0	9.2	9.6	10.1
9	1.2	6098		300.1			1800.1			4.9			8.4	
10	1.2	6098	395.7			2255.7			4.1			9.1		
11	1.2	6098	398.8			2230.6			5.1			9.6		
12	1.2	6098	400.6			2298.5			6.0			8.4		
13	1.2	6098			330.3			1967.2			5.7			11.1
14	1.2	6098			386.0			2021.1			5.0			10.4
15	1.2	6098	421.3			2437.7			4.5			8.2		
16	1.2	6098	413.5			2400.3			4.9			8.4		
17	1.2	6098	395.9			2320.6			5.1			9.8		
18	1.2	6098	400.9			2321.1			5.7			7.5		
19	1.2	6098			335.7			1970.5			6.2			10.6
20	1.2	6098		355.9			2040.6			4.5			9.7	
21	1.2	6098	400.6			2356.2			4.3			8.0		
22	1.2	6098			323.3			1850.6			6.0			10.5

Sl.No.	Seed rate (Kg/ha)	No.of plants/ha	No.of pods/plant			Yield (Kg/ha)						<i>M.vitrata</i> (larvae/plant)		
			V1	V2	V3	V1	V2	V3	V1	V2	V3	V1	V2	V3
23	1.2	6098	467.5			2765.1			5.0			7.5		
24	1.2	6098			210.3			1784.5			6.4			11.0
25	1.2	6098			170.1			1612.2			6.0			12.0
		Mean	403.5	361.9	325.2	2388.3	2163.2	1923.7	4.4	4.4	5.4	8.7	9.6	10.7
Local	12.00	75000	360.4	210.6	180.6	1358.5	1265.5	1000.5	8.1	8.3	9.5	14.5	16.5	18.5

V1: BSMR-736; V2: GRG-811; V3:ICPH-2740

Table 2. Statistical analysis of agronomic parameters and insect pest incidence

Character	Mean	Range	Std.deviation	Std.error	t value
Spacing (m)					
Number of pods/plant					
1.8x0.9	394.64	345-450	25.24	8.95	8.73*
0.45x0.1	317.5	270-361			
Pod yield (kg/ha)					
1.8x0.9	2401.85	2010.22-2845	279.65	99.16	8.98*
0.45x0.1	1511.01	1325.55-1832.03			
<i>Helicoverpa armizera</i> population (No. insects/plant)					
1.8x0.9	3.70	3-4.8	1.27	0.45	14.4*
0.45x0.1	10.18	9-12.45			
<i>Maruca vitrata</i> population (No. insects/plant)					
1.8x0.9	9.02	7.11-10.11	1.84	0.65	13.27*
0.45x0.1	17.65	14-20.5			